

A DIGITAL PLATFORM TO TRANSFORM DATA INTO A BETTER HEALTHCARE EXPERIENCE

**Furkan
Karaca**

h.f.karaca@tilburguniversity.edu

**Jelles
Duin**

j.g.duin@tilburguniversity.edu

**Lucas
Schuermans**

l.d.schuermans@tilburguniversity.edu

**Thorsten
Bär**

t.e.bar@tilburguniversity.edu

Abstract

The Dutch government promotes inclusive communication, ensuring everyone can access and understand information, regardless of background or abilities. This approach is also essential in healthcare, where patients have the right to view and understand their medical records. Healthcare professionals are not adapting the language to be clear and straightforward and avoiding unnecessary jargon. If this were the case, public services and healthcare would become more accessible, enabling better participation and understanding for all individuals.

The main research objective is to explore how data can be transformed into actionable information for various stakeholders in the healthcare process. This involves examining the alignment of data with specific requirements and identifying these requirements per stakeholder, budgetary considerations, tools, and legal regulations. A key focus is understanding the role of digital platforms in optimising this transformation, with particular emphasis on how they help meet stakeholder requirements, which is the primary area of investigation.

When analysing these topics, the research adopts a mixed-method approach. A systematic literature review of academic publications, industry reports, and policy papers provides the theoretical foundation. Quantitative analysis is made using surveys to gather information about patient insights, struggles, wants, and needs. To find out how the "Algemene verordening

gegevensbescherming" (AVG) and the Dutch Ministry of Public Health, Welfare, and Sport regulate data privacy and healthcare information, the study also uses comparative analysis.

The expected outcome of this study offers assistance in converting healthcare data into usable information for patients, medical professionals, and policymakers. It will also discuss the financial limitations and obstacles to long-term investment that impede the successful implementation of digital platforms in healthcare settings. Therefore, the research aims to improve inclusive communication by simplifying medical procedures and

enhancing access to essential information. This will be accomplished by providing a framework for an exclusive adapting generative AI tool trained by patients and other stakeholder data to transform the given medical data into useful information. The results will lay the groundwork for future studies concentrating on streamlining the integration of digital platforms in healthcare services, encouraging interaction and decision-making among stakeholders in healthcare sectors.

Digital platforms can assist in transforming healthcare data into meaningful insights for patients, providers, and policymakers. By addressing the specific needs of these stakeholders, these platforms highlight critical challenges in communication and access, along with the following financial and regulatory difficulties: AVG, GDPR, different types of ISO norms, and financial support and permission from the Dutch Ministry of public health,

welfare, and sport. This research advocates for inclusive strategies to boost patient engagement and informed decision-making. These findings improve understanding and set the stage for future inquiries into optimising digital integration within healthcare systems.

By attending to the stakeholders' requirements, this research adds value by optimising digital systems for better information management and decision-making. Thus, it is relevant for the conference about digital platforms as it researches the role of digital platforms in improving data accessibility and communication within the healthcare sector.

Keywords

Digital health · e-health · Health information and communication · Digital Platforms · AI · Artificial Intelligence · Digital Healthcare

List of abbreviations

AI - Artificial Intelligence

AVG - Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (General Data Protection Regulation in Dutch)

CBS - Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (Statistics Netherlands)

CD - Communication Difficulties

CHD - Complex Healthcare Data

COPD - Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

CVD - Cardiovascular disease

EU - European Union

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

HGIT - Healthcare Digital Interface Tools

HIPAA - Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act

IDD - Intellectual and Developmental Disorders

IUG - Information Understanding Gap

IZA - Integraal Zorgakkoord (Integrated Care Agreement)

LLM - Large Language Model

MBO - Middelbaar Beroepsonderwijs (Intermediate Vocational Education)

SLE - Systemic Lupus Erythematosus

WO - Wetenschappelijk Onderwijs (University-level Education)

Introduction

The importance of effective communication in healthcare has increased in recent years, motivated by the growing need for accessible and understandable medical information for various stakeholders. The capacity of patients to understand their medical records is essential for informed decision-making and active engagement in their care. However, communication in healthcare frequently poses substantial challenges for patients, healthcare providers, policymakers, and insurance companies. Obstacles like medical terminology can induce uncertainty and worry in patients, hindering their ability to make educated decisions (Rosenberg, 2023; Kolen, 2014). Furthermore, stakeholders, such as caregivers and healthcare professionals, may encounter challenges obtaining accurate information due to privacy restrictions like the GDPR and AVG, leading to confusion and avoidable errors (Bauder et al., 2023). For example, according to CommunicatieRijk, inclusive communication underscores the necessity of modifying language and procedures to guarantee that all individuals, irrespective of their background or skills, can understand and interact with information (Ministerie van Algemene Zaken, 2023). This notion is essential in healthcare, as transparent, inclusive communication may empower patients and reduce misunderstandings (Kwame & Petrucka, 2021). Despite advancements in digital technology designed to enhance healthcare communication, a significant gap persists in the successful implementation of these technologies to address the entire needs of all patients and stakeholders (Bauder et al., 2023).

This paper analyses the optimisation of digital platforms to convert complex healthcare data into accessible and comprehensible information for diverse stakeholders. The current literature addresses concerns such as medical terminology and regulatory compliance. However, there has been insufficient investigation into how digital solutions may effectively resolve these issues for stakeholders with differing degrees of healthcare literacy. This paper addresses this gap by suggesting techniques that enhance the accessibility and usability of medical data using digital technologies while complying with privacy and data protection rules, thereby facilitating more inclusive communication in healthcare. Additionally, this paper evaluates how digital platforms might enhance communication among all stakeholders, including caregivers and medical professionals, while adhering to strict privacy regulations such as GDPR and AVG. Finally, the paper aims to offer actionable

solutions for enhancing patient involvement and improving health outcomes with optimal digital technologies. This research seeks to enhance and expand the discourse on the effective implementation of digital platforms, focusing on practical applications that previous studies have frequently neglected.

Problem statement

Although clear communication is universally acknowledged as necessary, patients in healthcare settings often face significant barriers that hinder their ability to comprehend essential information quickly. For instance, the use of medical jargon and complex language continues to be a key barrier for patients, causing misunderstandings and frustration (Rosenberg, 2023; Kolen, 2014). Despite the promising advantages of advanced technology in transforming healthcare communication, there remains a considerable deficiency in the effective implementation of these innovations to address all patient requirements (Bauder et al., 2023). Current research primarily focuses on theoretical frameworks or broad solutions but lacks practical, actionable strategies for the application of digital platforms that can address these challenges directly. For example, while inclusive communication is frequently advocated in healthcare literature, it is often not implemented to directly improve patients' understanding and access to their health information (Kwame & Petrucka, 2021). While the challenges posed by medical terminology and privacy regulations are commonly discussed, insufficient attention is given to how digital platforms can fix these issues. Research suggests that platforms must be adaptable and user-friendly to bridge the gap between patients of varying literacy levels and healthcare providers, but practical implementations remain sparse (Baker et al., 1996).

There exists a deficiency in the assessment of the practical application of digital platforms for translating complex medical information into understandable content for individuals with varying levels of healthcare knowledge in a sufficiently impactful manner. However, more emphasis should be placed on the potential of digital solutions to enhance communication for patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals, ensuring that all stakeholders gain from more inclusive communication channels (Posch et al., 2020). Furthermore, prior research neglected to address how these digital platforms can improve communication among all stakeholders, including carers and healthcare workers, and how they can be

tailored to meet specific needs across a diverse patient population, all while adhering to privacy requirements such as the GDPR (Bauder et al., 2023).

Method

This study uses a mixed-method approach that integrates a systematic literature review, surveys, and a regulatory case analysis to investigate how digital platforms can improve inclusive access to communication in healthcare. This combination of methods was selected to ensure full comprehension of the challenges posed by complex healthcare data (CHD) and the potential of digital tools to address the information understanding gap (IUG).

The initial phase of the study involved a systematic literature review, the main objective of which was to identify and examine existing knowledge regarding AI-driven data transformation techniques and the financial and regulatory challenges associated with digital platforms. To maximise the studies' relevance, the review concentrated on studies published within the last 10 years and utilised databases such as Web of Science, WorldCat, and Google Scholar. The following keywords were included in the search: "AI in healthcare," "inclusive communication," and "telehealth regulation." Academic articles and industry reports were prioritised, while non-academic sources provided practical insights into Dutch and European healthcare contexts. The findings were synthesised into crucial themes, including the role of AI in simplifying medical terminology, the design and functionality of digital platforms, and the challenges of compliance with GDPR and AVG regulations. These insights informed the broader framework of the study and provided context for the practical application of digital tools.

The second stage of the research involved conducting a survey with the objective of gaining insights from both patients and healthcare professionals. The objective of the study was to research the experiences of patients with CHD, the communication challenges they face, and their preferences for digital platforms. The survey consisted of 5-point Likert scale questions, which were created with the objective of establishing a balance between qualitative depth and measurable outcomes.

The participants were selected using convenience sampling, with the inclusion criteria being that they were Dutch-speaking

adults aged 18 and above. The survey was sent out via Google Forms and distributed via the WhatsApp messaging platform, with the survey remaining open for a period of three days (23–25 November 2024). A total of 38 responses were collected, and the participants' demographic information (including age, gender, and educational background) was included to provide additional context for the findings.

In the final phase of the study, the findings from the previous phases were used to inform a case analysis. This phase showed how AI tools can be used to simplify complex medical information. In particular, ChatGPT 4.0 was used to rewrite complex diagnoses in a more accessible style, thereby addressing the issues identified in the survey.

For example, a term like "multisystemic autoimmune disease" was simplified into a clear, concise explanation that survey participants could easily understand. This practical application accentuated the potential of AI-driven tools to reduce the IUG while highlighting the significance of maintaining compliance with data privacy regulations such as GDPR and AVG. The analysis also explored the limitations of these tools, including the risks of misinformation and algorithmic "hallucinations," stressing the need for well-defined validation processes.

To increase the generalisability of the findings, the study adopted a triangulation strategy where data from the literature review, survey, and case analysis were cross-checked. This ensured that the findings were consistent and increased the reliability of the conclusions. In addition, a detailed record of the survey questions, literature search, and case analysis ensures that the study is replicable and provides a foundation for future research.

In light of the findings presented in this study, the methodology used in this paper offers insight into how digital platforms and AI-enabled solutions can help minimise communication barriers in healthcare. The study shows how these technologies can support patient engagement with healthcare information while highlighting the necessity to guarantee that innovations are relevant, safe, and appropriate in the context of ethical and regulatory considerations.

Research question

The research is centred on understanding how digital platforms can address the

communication challenges posed by complex healthcare data. As patients increasingly struggle to navigate and understand the critical information necessary for informed decision-making, the complexity of healthcare data often acts as a significant barrier. This issue is particularly pronounced for individuals with varying health literacy, language skills, or disabilities. In this context, digital platforms, especially those leveraging artificial intelligence (AI), have the potential to reduce these gaps and improve access to healthcare information. The central research question guiding this study is: *What influence can a digital platform have in reducing the communication gap created by complex healthcare data?*

To explore this question, the study investigates several aspects of digital healthcare platforms, including their functionality, design, and impact. The research is divided into the following sub-research questions:

Understanding the Communication Gap:

The study first seeks to understand the challenges patients face in comprehending complex healthcare data, as highlighted by survey results. This will provide a clearer picture of the barriers patients experience when trying to make sense of medical information.

Role of Digital Platforms: Next, the research explores how digital platforms can simplify complex healthcare data, making it more accessible for patients with varying levels of literacy and different disabilities.

Incorporation of AI: A key aspect of the study is the integration of AI into digital platforms. The research aims to explore how AI-driven tools can simplify medical terminology, transforming it into layperson-friendly language. It also looks at how AI can improve personalisation in healthcare communication, ensuring that platforms can cater to the diverse needs of different patient populations.

Regulatory and Ethical Considerations: The study acknowledges the importance of regulatory frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG). It examines how these regulations influence the design and functionality of AI-driven tools in healthcare communication, ensuring that patient data is protected while still enabling the platform to function effectively.

Practical Implementation: The research also identifies the main barriers to adopting digital platforms in healthcare, drawing on both survey

data and existing literature. This will help pinpoint the challenges that need to be addressed for successful implementation.

Measuring Effectiveness: Finally, the study investigates how the introduction of digital platforms influences the relationship between complex healthcare data and the information understanding gap. By measuring the effectiveness of these platforms, the research aims to assess whether they can truly reduce the gap and improve communication.

By addressing these sub-questions, the research seeks to provide actionable insights into the potential of digital platforms to make healthcare information more inclusive and accessible. The study also explores how these platforms can be designed to meet regulatory requirements while leveraging AI to enhance communication. Ultimately, the goal is to contribute to the development of digital tools that reduce communication gaps, empower patients, and facilitate more informed healthcare decisions.

Conceptual model & Theory

The conceptual model that is made to understand the effectiveness of digital platforms on this issue consists of three variables: Complex Healthcare Data, Information Understanding Gap and Healthcare Digital Interface tool.

Complex healthcare data encompasses diverse and extensive information generated within healthcare, including structured and unstructured data from patient records, diagnostic imaging, laboratory results, and patient-reported outcomes. Due to its heterogeneity and sensitivity, such data is challenging to process and interpret, requiring robust methods to ensure meaningful analysis and privacy compliance (Demirbaga et al., 2024).

The information understanding gap in healthcare is a communication gap that represents misunderstandings or disconnects between healthcare providers, patients, and caregivers. It often arises from differences in language, health literacy, or a lack of accessible information. Addressing this gap is critical to improving patient engagement, adherence to treatment, and healthcare outcomes (Rosenberg, 2023; Kolen, 2014).

A healthcare digital interface tool enables patients, providers, and other stakeholders to interact, access, and manage health-related information. This type of digital platform facilitates patient-provider communication, record access, telemedicine, and data sharing, making healthcare more accessible and patient-centred (Huxley et al., 2015).

The complexity of medical information often includes abstract terminology, detailed instructions, and complicated data. Patients or other stakeholders, particularly those with intellectual and developmental disorders (IDD) and communication difficulties (CD), have problems processing and understanding medical information (Shady et al., 2022). This complexity enlarges the communication gap, creating barriers to health literacy and limiting patients' ability to make healthcare decisions. Healthcare professionals are primarily untrained in simplified or alternative communication methods and heavily use standard medical language and traditional communication practices as studied. Without the implementation of accessible communication strategies, such as using everyday language, visual aids, or assistive communication services, patients with IDD/CD often have a negative experience regarding healthcare communication (Shady et al., 2022). Within this conceptual model, the CHD acts as an independent variable that influences the dependent variable information understanding gap, meaning the more complex medical information becomes, the more significant the information understanding gap shall be.

Healthcare digital interface tools in the form of digital platforms influence the information understanding gap (IUG) in healthcare by providing tools that facilitate interactions between clinicians and patients, improving access to and the management of complex health data (CHD). These platforms can bridge gaps by offering flexible and efficient communication methods, such as video consultations and email, which help overcome barriers like physical access and stigma. However, their effectiveness may vary

depending on the user's digital literacy and the quality of the pre-existing clinician-patient relationship. The paper "*Digital Communication between Clinician and Patient and the Impact on Marginalised Groups*" explains how digital tools can improve or limit communication depending on context, illustrating their potential to address access issues while recognising that they cannot eliminate all communication barriers (Huxley et al., 2015).

The proposed conceptual model hypothesises that complex healthcare data (CHD) will increase the information understanding gap (IUG) due to its inherent complexity and difficulty. This gap is particularly pronounced in patients with intellectual and developmental disorders (IDD) or communication difficulties (CD), such as language barriers, who may struggle to process and understand complex medical information. However, healthcare digital interface tools (HGIT) are expected to moderate this relationship. When these digital tools are used effectively, they can reduce the gap by offering clearer, more accessible forms of communication, such as simplified text or video explanations. This moderating effect is shown in the conceptual model as an interaction term. It shows that the relationship between CHD and IUG changes based on how digital tools are used and how well they work.

Summarised, the primary objective of this research is to examine the impact of complex healthcare data (CHD) on the information understanding gap (IUG) with a moderator of healthcare digital inference tools (HGIT). Therefore, the following hypotheses were proposed:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Healthcare digital interface (HGIT) tools negatively affect the relationship between complex healthcare data (CHD) and the information understanding gap (IUG).

Results

This section presents the findings of the survey research, focusing on how Healthcare Digital Interface Tools (HDIT) influence the relationship between complex healthcare data (CHD) and the information understanding gap (IUG) among Dutch adults. The results are complemented by insights from the literature review, which highlights the role of large language models (LLMs) in simplifying complex medical information. Additionally, a regulatory case study underscores the legal and ethical considerations, particularly the impact of GDPR and EU ePrivacy directives on the implementation of AI-driven healthcare tools.

Literature Review on Data Transformation Methods

Transforming complex medical information into accessible language is vital for improving patients' understanding. Recent studies highlight that LLMs have shown promise in simplifying complex medical information across various contexts, including cardiovascular disease (CVD) prevention, patient education, and the transformation of radiology reports into plain language (Lyu et al., 2023; Mishra et al., 2024).

While LLMs offer opportunities, they also introduce risks related to the quality, accuracy, and accessibility of the information they generate. To use these tools successfully depends on the optimisation of the prompts, which directly influence the completeness and reliability of the output (Mishra et al., 2024).

This study uses the example of an LLM model (ChatGPT 4.0) in the survey research (later on) to illustrate the use of LLMs in simplifying complex medical information. In it, an LLM model was employed to adapt a clinical diagnosis and its description into more accessible language. Specifically, the first and last item in Table 3 are adapted using ChatGPT 4.0, demonstrating how HDIT (Healthcare Digital Inference Tools) would transform complex medical terminology. Below is the adaptation of the diagnoses:

Original Text

Diagnose: Multisystemische auto-immuunziekte met primaire manifestatie van systemische lupus erythematoses (SLE) en secundaire overlap met Sjögren-syndroom.

Samenvatting van het klinisch beeld:

De patiënt presenteerde zich met een multisymptomatisch ziektebeeld bestaande uit artralgieën, persisterende vermoeidheid, fotosensitiviteit, en recidiverende mucosale ulceraties. Daarnaast werden droge ogen (keratoconjunctivitis sicca) en xerostomie vastgesteld, passend bij een secundaire Sjögren-overlap.

LLM simplified text

Diagnose: Een auto-immuunziekte die meerdere systemen in het lichaam aantast, met als hoofdziekte systemische lupus erythematoses (SLE), samen met kenmerken van het Sjögren-syndroom.

Samenvatting van de symptomen:

De patiënt heeft last van gewrichtspijn, aanhoudende vermoeidheid, overgevoeligheid

voor zonlicht en terugkerende zweren in de mond. Daarnaast zijn er klachten van droge ogen en een droge mond, wat past bij het Sjögren-syndroom als bijkomende aandoening.

The simplification of complex medical information aligns with the findings from the survey results, where participants indicated struggles with understanding complex medical information. As demonstrated in Table 3, the simplified language made the information more understandable, which correlates with the survey results, indicating that simplified medical descriptions led to higher levels of understanding (see results section for detailed survey insights).

Survey Research

The survey questions for this study were designed explicitly for a Dutch-speaking audience. Therefore, the survey was conducted entirely in Dutch to ensure clarity, accessibility, and relevance for the target participants. For this conference paper, the survey questions and results have been carefully translated into English to maintain the accuracy and intent of the original content.

Sample and data collection

The unit of analysis for this research consists of Dutch adults aged 18 and older. A non-probability sampling method, specifically convenience sampling, was employed to select participants. Data was collected using a Google Forms survey, which was distributed via WhatsApp. A total of 38 participants (n=38) completed the survey. The survey remained accessible online for three days, from November 23, 2024, to November 25, 2024.

Measurement

The study explores the relationship between health literacy challenges and the comprehension of medical information through a series of survey questions designed to assess participants' understanding of medical terminology and complex diagnoses. These questions were categorised into three distinct tables for clarity and structure.

Table 1 provides the questions asked to determine whether the sample is representative of the population studied. It includes questions on the participants' general background, such as their experience with medical terminology and healthcare communication.

Table 2 outlines the questions and statements that examine the relationship between 'complex healthcare data' and the 'information understanding gap.' Participants were first asked about their ability to understand medical

terms, highlighting difficulties that could inform improvements in healthcare communication. Another question explored how often medical information was perceived as unclear, emphasising the need for clearer communication to enhance understanding. To evaluate comprehension of complex medical terminology, participants were asked about their understanding of the given diagnosis of "Multisystemic autoimmune disease." This served as a baseline measure of comprehension for complex terms and helped identify gaps in understanding that could be addressed through language simplification strategies. A follow-up question presented in Table 3 assessed comprehension of "Multisystemic autoimmune disease (simplified)," testing the effect of simplified language on comprehension and demonstrating the effectiveness of simplifying medical terminology to improve understanding.

Similarly, participants were asked about their understanding of "Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)," which provided another baseline measure of comprehension. A subsequent question about the simplified version of "Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) (simplified)" allowed for a comparison of comprehension between complex and simplified terms, reinforcing the value of simplifying medical information to bridge the understanding gap. Both simplifications were made using ChatGPT 4.0 to emulate how the HDIT would simplify the medical jargon into a more familiar language.

Table 3 presents the questions and statements to determine the 'healthcare digital interface tool' effect on the relationship between 'complex healthcare data' and the 'information understanding gap.' Participants were asked about their willingness to use digital platforms and AI-based tools for medical communication in the future. This explored their openness to adopting digital tools and AI to improve healthcare communication. Additionally, the study assessed the participants' trust in digital platforms for storing and displaying medical information. This measure aimed to evaluate how trust in digital tools might influence the relationship between health literacy challenges and comprehension, ultimately shedding light on the potential role of digital tools in improving understanding.

The level of measurement for both relationships in Tables 2 and 3 is interval, meaning the responses are measured on a scale that assumes equal intervals between points, providing precise data on the strength of these relationships.

Together, these questions aim to uncover patterns in health literacy challenges, comprehension difficulties, and attitudes towards digital tools, offering valuable insights for enhancing communication and understanding in healthcare settings.

Table 1: Demographic questions

Question	Measurement
Age	18-26, 27-40, 41-64, 65+
Gender	Male/female/prefer not to say
Education level	None/MBO/HBO/WO/Other

Table 2: measurement relationship IV → DV

Question	Measurement
Statement: I struggle with reading and understanding medical terms.	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)
How often do you find the medical information you receive unclear?	5-point Likert scale (Always - Never)
Diagnosis: Multisystemic autoimmune disease.	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)
Diagnosis: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD).	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)

Table 3: Measurement of the effect of the Moderator

Question	Measurement
Diagnosis: Multisystemic autoimmune disease (simplified).	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)
Statement: I would be willing to use digital platforms & AI-based tools for medical communication in the future.	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)
To what extent do you trust digital platforms for storing and displaying medical information?	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)
Diagnosis: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) (simplified).	5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree - Strongly disagree)

Data findings

After the data was collected using a 5-point Likert scale, it was transformed into a numerical scale ranging from -1 to 1. This transformation was performed to ensure that the data were compatible with the statistical analysis requirements.

The transformation process was performed based on the context and framing of each question. Responses were transformed as follows: "Strongly agree" and "Strongly disagree" were assigned values of -1 or 1, depending on whether the question was negatively or positively framed. "Agree" and "Disagree" were assigned values of -0.5 or 0.5, respectively, while "Neutral" was given a value of 0. This approach ensured consistent comparisons across variables, which in turn supported the reliability of the analysis. The results of the questions were summed up based on which relation they had an influence on (see Appendix 1).

The descriptive statistics indicate that the mean value for the relationship between CHD and IUG before the implementation of HGIT tools (Relation 1) was 0.0458. After introducing HGIT

tools (Relation 2), this mean value decreased to -0.3654, reflecting a noticeable weakening in the relationship between CHD and IUG. This difference is visually represented in Figure 1, providing a clear illustration of the change.

Figure 1: Average of relation 1 vs relation 2

A one-tailed paired t-test was conducted to assess the statistical significance of the observed difference. The results showed a t-statistic of -6.2697 and a p-value of 8.39×10^{-8} . The p-value is significantly below the threshold of 0.05, which supports the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0). The results provide substantial evidence that the implementation of HGIT tools has a statistically significant impact on the relationship between CHD and IUG, thereby supporting the hypothesis that these tools have a negative effect on this relationship.

Regulatory case study

Large Language Model AI integrated into digital health platforms offers significant opportunities but raises complex legal and liability issues. Many legal frameworks, including the EU ePrivacy Directive and the General Data Protection Regulation, cover these issues. Understanding how these regulations interact is critical to ensuring patient safety, privacy, and trust in AI-driven healthcare.

According to Shumway and Hartman, one primary concern with systems based on LLM is the existence of algorithmic "hallucinations," where artificial intelligence produces misinformation or deceiving information, which will lead to misdiagnosis and improper treatment. Such incidences increase physician liability when clinical decisions depend on results from AI. Another concern is the ambiguity within AI-developed guidance. Given that LLMs often provide interpretive advice, the recommendations generally need independent judgment on behalf of the healthcare providers to avoid misuse or misapplication of the AI insight (Shumway & Hartman, 2024).

The legal framework from which these challenges stem begins with the EU Directive 2002/58/EC, establishing rules that guarantee privacy in electronic communications relevant to healthcare platforms. It provides the principle of secrecy of communication, imposing the obligation on service providers not to allow unauthorised access to data. It also promotes a consent-based approach to data processing, with guarantees for the users' control over their personal information. The directive also sets formal data security obligations, under which patient data must be protected from loss, theft, and unauthorised access. While focused on electronic communications, the ePrivacy Directive complements the GDPR by reinforcing principles such as consent and data minimisation, which are crucial when healthcare platforms integrate AI-driven tools (European Union, 2002).

Another cornerstone of the regulatory framework is the GDPR, providing an all-encompassing set of rules for processing personal data in the EU. Its scope embraces sensitive patient data, requiring it to be processed lawfully, transparently, and legitimately. The GDPR demands the implementation of the purpose limitation principle, data minimisation, and accuracy: it shall process only the data required for legitimate purposes determined in advance. Patients have a right to access, correct, delete, or transfer their personal data, and controllers should be accountable for compliance. Other requirements for healthcare platforms using AI include carrying out Data Protection Impact Assessments for large-scale sensitive data processing and transparency regarding how AI systems use patient data. The provisions also allow patients to contest fully automated decisions, which further calls for human intervention in critical medical scenarios. Non-compliance with the GDPR attracts heavy fines; thus, compliance with its provisions is paramount (European Union, 2016).

Breaches in GDPR could face fines of up to €20 million or 4% of the annual global turnover, whichever is higher (European Union, 2016).

Discussion

This study shows the significant potential of Healthcare Digital Interface Tools (HGITs) to address the challenges posed by Complex Healthcare Data (CHD). By simplifying medical jargon and making it easier for patients to understand, these tools are highly effective at narrowing the Information Understanding Gap (IUG). The results showing a drop in the mean

IUG value from 0.0458 to -0.3654 demonstrate their impact. This conclusion is further supported by strong statistical evidence, with a t-value of -6.2697 and a p-value of 8.39×10^{-8} . These findings confirm that simplifying complex medical information is not only feasible but also a meaningful way to improve patient understanding.

Survey responses provide additional context and reinforce the value of these tools. Many participants expressed enthusiasm for adopting digital platforms and AI tools to help them understand their health better, indicating a positive attitude toward innovation. However, the data also highlighted a common issue: many patients continue to struggle with medical terminology. More than half of the respondents reported regularly finding medical information unclear, echoing past research that identifies jargon as a key barrier to understanding (Rosenberg, 2023). This highlights an ongoing need for healthcare providers to focus on making communication clearer and more accessible for everyone.

The ChatGPT case study offers a practical example of how AI-driven tools can help address this challenge. By translating complex medical diagnoses into plain, everyday language, the tool made health information more manageable for respondents to understand and engage with. Complex healthcare data was simplified into clear, relatable descriptions that significantly improved comprehension. This supports the idea that simplifying medical language can effectively reduce the IUG. It also demonstrates the role large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT can play in creating a more inclusive approach to healthcare communication. These findings align with ongoing efforts in the Netherlands to improve healthcare accessibility through innovation.

Despite these promising results, some challenges need to be addressed to ensure these tools reach their full potential. One primary concern is trust. While many participants expressed optimism about AI-driven tools, others were sceptical about their accuracy, security, and the handling of personal information. These concerns are understandable, especially given the strict data privacy requirements of regulations like the GDPR and the Dutch AVG. These frameworks emphasise principles like transparency, data minimisation, and clear purpose, which add complexity to implementing AI systems in healthcare. For instance, healthcare platforms must ensure that AI operates in a clear and

understandable way, conduct thorough data protection assessments, and provide options for human oversight to maintain compliance.

Another concern is the risk of AI "hallucinations," where tools produce incorrect or misleading information. Such mistakes could lead to misdiagnoses and increase healthcare providers' liability risk. Tackling these issues will require robust validation processes and clear guidelines for using AI in clinical settings. While these challenges are significant, they are not insurmountable. Existing legal frameworks like the GDPR provide a solid foundation for balancing innovation with safety, ensuring that AI tools can improve communication without compromising patient trust.

The broader implications of these findings are equally noteworthy. By simplifying medical information, HGITs can empower patients to make better-informed decisions, improving their health literacy. These tools can also enhance communication between patients and healthcare providers, reduce misunderstandings, and lower the likelihood of errors. Additionally, HGITs have the potential to address health disparities. By tailoring communication to meet the needs of marginalised groups—such as people with disabilities, non-native speakers, or those with limited literacy—these tools can make healthcare more equitable and accessible.

Healthcare providers and policymakers also stand to gain from using HGITs. For providers, these tools can save time by reducing the need to explain complex terms repeatedly, allowing for more personalised care. For policymakers, integrating HGITs into healthcare aligns with broader goals of digital transformation, such as improving patient satisfaction, reducing administrative tasks, and making the healthcare system more efficient overall.

Unlocking these benefits will require collaboration. Healthcare providers, developers, and policymakers must work together to create tools that are effective, straightforward, and inclusive. Training programs for healthcare professionals will also be essential to ensure these tools are used effectively in practice. Building trust through transparency and clear communication with patients about how these tools work will be crucial for encouraging widespread adoption.

In summary, this study demonstrates the ability of HGITs to transform healthcare communication by making complex information easier for patients to understand. While

challenges such as trust and regulatory requirements persist, they do not diminish the power of these tools to simplify medical language and close the IUG. With the right strategies—combining innovation, collaboration, and transparency—HGITs can contribute to a healthcare system that is more inclusive, patient-focused, and effective.

Conclusion

This research set out to explore how digital platforms could help bridge the communication gap caused by complex healthcare data (CHD). By focusing on the role of Healthcare Digital Interface Tools (HGIT), we aimed to understand how these tools can make medical information more accessible and manageable for patients and other stakeholders. Although the study uncovered some promising possibilities, there were also clear limitations that should be addressed in future research.

One of the biggest challenges we faced was the method of sampling. Because we relied on convenience sampling, the group of participants wasn't fully representative of the broader Dutch population. For example, 76% of our respondents had HBO or WO educational backgrounds, compared to 37% of the population (CBS, 2024). Similarly, 72% of the participants were between 18-40 years old, a clear overrepresentation of younger adults. This limits how generalisable our findings are. On top of that, the limited time available for the study impacted the reliability of our data. For instance, responses collected over the days showed inconsistencies, with a weak negative Pearson correlation (-0.2631) between the second and third days, which suggests that participants' answers were not stable across those days. For future research, we recommend using more representative sampling methods, like stratified or random sampling, and extending the timeline to collect more robust data for better reliability and validity of the research.

That said, the study also shows the potential of digital tools and AI-driven platforms to make healthcare communication more inclusive. Large Language Models (LLMs), in particular, were effective in simplifying complex medical terms into language that's easier for people to understand. This demonstrates that technology can play a significant role in breaking down communication barriers, which is a key step toward more equitable healthcare.

However, there are still important concerns. Data privacy is one of the biggest challenges,

as well as ensuring that AI tools are trustworthy and accurate. Issues like “hallucinations,” where AI tools produce misleading or false information, are serious risks that need to be addressed. While frameworks like the GDPR and AVG provide strong guidelines, there’s still a lot of work to be done to ensure that these tools can be used safely and ethically in real-world healthcare settings.

Looking ahead, there are plenty of areas for future research. One important direction is developing digital tools that work for diverse groups, including people with disabilities, non-native speakers, and patients with varying levels of health literacy. Another area is figuring out how these platforms can support not just patients but also other stakeholders like healthcare providers, insurers, and policymakers. Finally, exploring the financial and infrastructural challenges of implementing these platforms will be crucial to making them sustainable in the long term.

What this study ultimately shows is that simplifying healthcare communication isn’t just a technical challenge—it’s about empowering people. By making medical information easier to understand, digital platforms can help patients make more informed decisions, reduce

misunderstandings, and improve trust between patients and providers. This doesn’t just benefit individuals; it also has the potential to create a more efficient and inclusive healthcare system overall.

In conclusion, while there is still a lot to improve, this research highlights the exciting possibilities of digital platforms in healthcare. By addressing the limitations of this study and continuing to refine these tools, future research can help ensure that healthcare communication becomes clearer, more accessible, and more equitable for everyone. Collaboration between researchers, developers, and policymakers will be key to achieving these goals, paving the way for a healthcare system that works better for everyone.

References

- Baker, D. W., Parker, R. M., Williams, M. V., Pitkin, K., Parikh, N. S., Coates, W., & Imara, M. (1996). The health care experience of patients with low literacy. *Archives of Family Medicine*, 5(6), 329–334. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archfami.5.6.329>
- Bauder, L., Giangobbe, K., & Asgary, R. (2023). Barriers and gaps in effective health communication at both public health and healthcare delivery levels during epidemics and pandemics: Systematic review. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*, 17, e395. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dmp.2023.61>
- Blandford, A., Wesson, J., Amalberti, R., AlHazme, R., & Allwihan, R. (2020). Opportunities and challenges for telehealth within, and beyond, a pandemic. *The Lancet Global Health*, 8(11), e1364–e1365. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30362-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30362-4)
- Burr, C., Morley, J., Taddeo, M., & Floridi, L. (2020). Digital Psychiatry: Risks and opportunities for public health and wellbeing. *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society*, 1(1), 21–33. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tts.2020.2977059>
- CBS. (2024, 4 september). Wat is het onderwijsniveau van Nederland? - Nederland in cijfers 2024. Wat Is het Onderwijsniveau van Nederland? - Nederland in Cijfers 2024 | CBS. <https://longreads.cbs.nl/nederland-in-cijfers-2024/wat-is-het-onderwijsniveau-van-nederland/>
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. (z.d.). Mannen en vrouwen. Centraal Bureau Voor de Statistiek. <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/dashboard-bevolking/mannen-en-vrouwen#:~:text=Zie%20ook%20de%20bevolkingspiramide,meerderheid%2C%20op%20hogere%20leeftijden%20vrouwen.>
- Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. (z.d.-a). Leeftijdsverdeling. Centraal Bureau Voor de Statistiek. <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/dashboard-bevolking/leeftijd/bevolking>
- Demirbaga, Ü., Aujla, G. S., Jindal, A., & Kalyon, O. (2024). *Big Data Analytics: Theory, Techniques, Platforms, and Applications*. Springer Nature Switzerland AG. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-55639-5>
- European Union. (2002). Directive 2002/58/EC on privacy and electronic communications. Retrieved November 29, 2024, from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/NL/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002L0058>
- European Union. (2016). General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Retrieved November 29, 2024, from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/NL/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.119.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2016:119:TOC
- Huxley, C. J., Atherton, H., Watkins, J. A., & Griffiths, F. (2015). Digital communication between clinician and patient and the impact on marginalised groups: a realist review in general practice. *British Journal of General Practice*, 65(641), e813–e821. <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp15x687853>
- Kickbusch, I., Pelikan, J. M., Apfel, F., & Tsouros, A. D. (Eds.). (2013). *Health literacy: The solid facts*. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/326432/9789289000154-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Kolen, B. (2014, July). *Zorg voor beter begrip met minder jargon: Effecten van medisch jargon en medium op attitude, tekstbegrip en geloofwaardigheid bij gezondheidscommunicatie* [Master's thesis, Tilburg University]. Tilburg University Library.
- Kreps, G. L., & Neuhauser, L. (2010). New directions in eHealth communication: Opportunities and challenges. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 78(3), 329–336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2010.01.013>

- Kwame, A., & Petrucka, P. M. (2021). A literature-based study of patient-centered care and communication in nurse-patient interactions: Barriers, facilitators, and the way forward. *BMC Nursing*, 20(1), Article 158. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00684-2>
- Lyles, C. R., Sarkar, U., & Osborn, C. Y. (2014). Getting a Technology-Based Diabetes Intervention Ready for Prime Time: a Review of Usability Testing Studies. *Current Diabetes Reports*, 14(10). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-014-0534-9>
- Lyu, Q., Tan, J., Zapadka, M. E., Ponnatapura, J., Niu, C., Myers, K. J., Wang, G., & Whitlow, C. T. (2023). Translating radiology reports into plain language using ChatGPT and GPT-4 with prompt learning: results, limitations, and potential. *Visual Computing for Industry Biomedicine and Art*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42492-023-00136-5>
- Ministerie van Algemene Zaken. (2023, October 6). Inclusieve communicatie: Wat en hoe. *Inclusieve Communicatie* | *CommunicatieRijk*. <https://www.communicatierijk.nl/vakkennis/inclusieve-communicatie/inclusieve-communicatie>
- Mishra, V., Sarraju, A., Kalwani, N. M., & Dexter, J. P. (2024). Evaluation of prompts to simplify cardiovascular disease information using a large language model: Cross-Sectional Study (Preprint). *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 26, e55388. <https://doi.org/10.2196/55388>
- Posch, N., Horvath, K., Wratschko, K., Plath, J., Brodnig, R., & Siebenhofer, A. (2020). Written patient information materials used in general practices fail to meet acceptable quality standards. *BMC Family Practice*, 21(1), Article 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-020-1085-6>
- Rosenberg, K. (2023). Medical jargon may lead to confusion among patients. *AJN, American Journal of Nursing*, 123(3), 61. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.naj.0000921824.12151.35>
- Schouten, B. C., & Meeuwesen, L. (2006). Cultural differences in medical communication: A review of the literature. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 64(1-3), 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2005.11.014>
- Shady, K., Phillips, S., & Newman, S. (2022). Barriers and Facilitators to Healthcare Access in Adults with Intellectual and Developmental Disorders and Communication Difficulties: an Integrative Review. *Review Journal Of Autism And Developmental Disorders*, 11(1), 39-51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-022-00324-8>
- Shumway, D. O., & Hartman, H. J. (2024). Medical malpractice liability in large language model artificial intelligence: legal review and policy recommendations. *Journal of Osteopathic Medicine*, 124(7), 287-290. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jom-2023-0229>
- Smets, E. M., Menichetti, J., Lie, H. C., & Gerwing, J. (2023). What do we mean by "tailoring" of medical information during clinical interactions? *Patient Education And Counseling*, 119, 108092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2023.108092>
- Sørensen, K., Brand, H., Van den Broucke, S., Fullam, J., Doyle, G., Pelikan, J., Slonska, Z., van den Broucke, S., Agraifodis, D., Ioannidi, E., Kondilis, B., Cafferkey, K., Röethlin, F., Falcon, M., Tchamov, K., Zhekov, A., Droomers, M., Schuit, J., van der Heide, I., et al. (2012). Health literacy and public health: a systematic review and integration of definitions and models. *BMC Public Health*, 12, 80. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-80>
- Van der Heide, I., Heijmans, M., Schuit, A. J., Uiters, E., & Rademakers, J. (2013). Functional, interactive and critical health literacy: Varying relationships with self-reported health and healthcare utilisation. *BMC Public Health*, 13(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-1095>
- Van Der Heide, I., Rademakers, J., Schipper, M., Droomers, M., Sørensen, K., & Uiters, E. (2013b). Health literacy of Dutch adults: a cross sectional survey. *BMC Public Health*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-179>

Appendix 1 - Results after transforming

Time	Age	Gender	Edu	Table 1	Table 2
2024-11-23 17:30:56		41 - 64	Man	MBO 0	0
2024-11-23 17:35:09		27 - 40	Man	MBO 0,125	-0,375
2024-11-23 17:55:47		18 - 26	Vrouw	WO -0,5	-0,5
2024-11-23 17:56:46		27 - 40	Man	HBO 0,25	-0,75
2024-11-23 18:00:50		41 - 64	Vrouw	HBO -0,5	-0,125
2024-11-23 18:07:02		18 - 26	Man	HBO 0,25	-0,625
2024-11-23 18:07:41		41 - 64	Vrouw	Geen 1	-0,375
2024-11-23 18:11:44		18 - 26	Man	WO 0	-0,125
2024-11-23 18:25:03		18 - 26	Man	WO -0,125	-0,75
2024-11-23 18:31:45		18 - 26	Man	HBO 1	1
2024-11-23 18:55:43		18 - 26	Man	HBO 0,375	-0,625
2024-11-23 19:02:12		18 - 26	Man	HBO 0,375	0,25
2024-11-23 19:14:10		18 - 26	Man	HBO 0,375	-0,25
2024-11-23 19:24:45		18 - 26	Man	MBO -0,125	-0,375
2024-11-23 20:05:08		41 - 64	Vrouw	Geen 0,125	-0,625
2024-11-23 20:09:49		27 - 40	Man	HBO 0,25	-0,5
2024-11-23 21:08:57		18 - 26	Man	HBO 0	-0,5
2024-11-23 22:04:38		27 - 40	Vrouw	HBO -0,25	-0,25
2024-11-23 22:51:32		18 - 26	Man	WO -0,125	-0,25
2024-11-24 00:41:13		27 - 40	Vrouw	MBO 0,25	-0,25
2024-11-24 01:24:23		27 - 40	Man	WO 0,25	0
2024-11-24 09:25:51		27 - 40	Man	HBO 0,375	-0,125
2024-11-24 09:54:29		41 - 64	Vrouw	MBO 0,25	-0,625
2024-11-24 18:16:44		41 - 64	Man	MBO 0	-0,5
2024-11-24 19:37:17		18 - 26	Man	WO 0	-0,5
2024-11-24 19:42:30		18 - 26	Vrouw	MBO -0,375	-0,375
2024-11-24 19:47:20		18 - 26	Man	WO -0,125	-0,5
2024-11-24 20:16:56		18 - 26	Vrouw	WO -0,25	-0,5
2024-11-24 21:54:42		65+	Man	WO 0	-0,125
2024-11-25 00:57:34		41 - 64	Man	MBO 0,625	-0,5
2024-11-25 12:49:45		65+	Vrouw	HBO -0,375	-0,25
2024-11-25 12:59:40		18 - 26	Man	WO -0,25	-0,5
2024-11-25 13:12:12		18 - 26	Man	WO -0,5	-0,125
2024-11-25 15:23:31		18 - 26	Vrouw	HBO 0,375	-0,75

2024-11-25 15:52:32	18 - 26	Vrouw WO	-0,5	-0,375
2024-11-25 17:33:17	18 - 26	Vrouw WO	-0,25	-0,75
2024-11-25 18:14:29	41 - 64	Vrouw WO	0	-0,625
2024-11-25 19:23:32	41 - 64	Man HBO	-0,375	-0,625
2024-11-25 20:35:47	18 - 26	Man HBO	0,125	-0,5